

Determination of drinking water-arsenic in nano gram level using flow injection analysis system atomic absorption spectrometry and an interpretation for the cause behind contamination

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Abstract : The ground water in arsenic infested zone, West Bengal, India is characterised by high iron, arsenic, calcium, magnesium and bi-carbonate with low chloride and sulphate. The pH is generally greater than 7. In this pH medium, iron tends to precipitate as hydroxide and arsenic may also co-precipitate with ferric hydroxide. Addition of hydrochloric acid is necessary to dissolve all iron, prior to arsenic analysis by flow injection analysis system - atomic absorption spectrometric method. Addition of sufficient KI in HCl medium is necessary to reduce all As⁵⁺ to As³⁺ state before analysis. The average practical detection limit of the FIAS-AAS method is 0.035 µg/L. The method itself is highly sensitive and sensitivity is 0.07 µg/L which is far better than many other methods such as flame atomic absorption, hydride generation atomic absorption spectrometric method and from the conventional spectrophotometric method. Shallow tubewell or well shows the highest peak in the bar graph.

Keywords : Arsenic, FIAS-AAS, contamination.

From the last decade, arsenic contamination in ground water in several districts of West Bengal¹⁻³, India pose a serious threat to the people. The reason behind it has not been till explored. Experts pointed out¹ that the ground water of intermediate aquifer is polluted with arsenic. Arsenic concentration is relatively high-in-clay and fine sand grains and the sand grains in arsenic infested aquifer are generally coated with iron and arsenic. However, the real source is still under scanner and not yet established. The thorough monitoring of arsenic in environmental, biological and food samples is important because arsenic compounds are used in agro industrial areas, metallurgical industry, in therapeutic and veterinary medicine⁴. So either from geo chemical processes or cumulative leaching of the used arsenicals in the soils contaminate our drinking water slowly, it is a burning question. Now it is our foremost task to determine all arsenic contamination in parts per billion level to resist the further contamination and to abstain people from drinking the poisoned water which causes skin cancer⁵, bladder cancer⁶ and ultimate death.

The interim maximum acceptable concentration for arsenic in drinking water is 0.025 mg/L¹ and guide line of WHO for arsenic is 0.01 mg/L⁷ maximum.

Among analytical techniques used in routine determination of arsenic, the common methods are spectrophotometric method⁸, hydride generation atomic absorption spectrometry¹⁰, inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry¹⁰, electrothermal atomic absorption spectrophotometry¹¹ and recently introduced most convenient and sensitive system is flow injection atomic absorption spectrometry (FIAS-AAS)¹².

When contamination causes several deaths^{2,3}, then rapid, accurate and cost-effective detection of arsenic in lowest level is necessary. In this study we are detailing a simple method to analyse drinking water supply for total arsenic with FIAS-Atomic Absorption Spectrometry.

We also co-relate our advance data with our earlier findings and try to come out a conclusion about the cause of vast arsenic contamination in ground water around the huge alluvial tract bound by Bhagirathi (Ganga) river in

the west, Malda District in the North and 24-Parganas in the South of W.B.

Results and discussion

Drinking water samples are randomly chosen and analysed and data are collected from 48 no. of samples. Each value is an average of three measurements with RSD < 5%. Bar graph is plotted from the data and shown in Fig. 1. This arsenic concentration versus different water source and different places bar graph (Fig. 1) indicated that shallow tubewell predominates the higher peak.

The practical detection limit for total arsenic is 0.035 $\mu\text{g/L}$ which is the lowest concentration of analyte that can be measured with reasonable confidence i.e. RSD < 5% for each three determination. The sensitivity of the method corresponding to 0.0044 absorbance unit is 0.07 $\mu\text{g/L}$. The method is highly sensitive and almost free from matrix effect and spectral interferences. Only careful operation and clean laboratories are the important conditions for precise analysis.

The sensitivity of conventional silver diethyl dithio carbamate⁸ method is 0.02 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. All sediment samples

Fig. 1. Bar graph for arsenic in drinking water sample of West Bengal.

were analysed by this method and represented in Table 2. The sensitivity of atomic absorption via gaseous hydride⁹ generation method is 0.001 µg/ml, whereas 0.003 µg/ml sensitivity was reported by Chakrabarty *et al.*² in their flow injection hydride generation atomic absorption method. The sensitivity of electrothermal atomic absorption spectrometry¹¹ is 0.06 µg/ml. So FIAS-AAS method is the best, precise and rapid method for arsenic determination.

Experimental

Instrumentation : Flow Injection Analysis System-Atomic Absorption Spectrometry was used for analysis of the collected water. The instrument used was of Perkin-Elmer AAS-Analyst 100 model with FIAS-100, attached with PC and AA winlab software for controlling total analytical system and results. HP deskjet printer is also attached with the instrument. An electrode less discharge lamp of arsenic was used for arsenic determination. The flow injection system¹² is used in atomic spectroscopy to compliment and extend the flame technique. FIAS itself transported the generated arsine (in the gas liquid separator) from the test solution to the chosen quartz cell-burner head atomiser, where the arsine was separated to arsenic and atomised by air-acetylene flame. The specific absorption was detected and modulated by photo multiplier tube (PMT) detector. Standard calibration curve in linear and non linear region were carried out with the help of AAwinlab software and thus arsenic concentration was determined directly from the instrument.

The instrumental parameters for analyses were listed in Table 1. The time of integration was 15 s for all the measurements. Peak height measurements were used for data calculation.

Reagent and chemicals : All reagents and the standard used were of spectroscopic grade and acids were of supra pure grade.

A solution of 0.2% NaBH₄ (E. Merck, Germany) prepared in 0.05% NaOH was used as main reducing agent (i.e. reduction of arsenic to AsH₃) and 10% (v/v) HCl was used as carrier solution. The flow rate maintained for both tetrahydroborate and hydrochloric acid was in 1 : 2 ratio. The ultimate carrier solution flow rate was 1 ml/min, high purity de-ionised water using Milli QTM water purification system (Millipore) was used throughout.

Arsenic stock solution (1000 mg/L) was prepared by dissolving 1.320 g As₂O₃ (Merck, Germany) in about 20 ml of 1.0 mol L⁻¹ NaOH. A volume of 50 ml of 0.5 mol

Table 1. FIAS-AAS : Analytical parameters for arsenic determination by FIAS

Spectrometer :	
Technique	AA
Integration time (s)	1.5
Data processing	Peak height, smoothing 0.5 s
Lamp	Electrode less discharge lamp
Slit (nm)	0.7 nm (low)
Wave length (nm)	193.7
FIAS system :	
Cell temp.	900 °C
Pump speed	120 rpm
Reagents :	
Carrier solution	10% (v/v) HCl
Reducing agent	0.2% NaBH ₄ in 0.05% NaOH solution
Sample solution	As ³⁺ in 10% (v/v) HCl
Sample volume	500 µL
Carrier gas flow rate	50 ml/min

L⁻¹ HCl was added to this solution and the volume was made up to 1000 ml with water.

5% (w/v) KI (AnalaR grade) solution was prepared for the reduction of As⁵⁺ to As³⁺ state.

Procedure :

Sample collection : Drinking water samples were collected from taps, tubewells, wells and rocky surfaces at random 250 ml each and kept in tarson bottle with addition of little concentrated HCl.

Sample preparation : Exactly 20 ml of water sample was taken in 100 mL glass beaker. 1 ml of concentrated supra pure HCl was added and the water sample was digested on a hot plate (maintained the temperature 80 °C) for 10 to 15 min to ensure all precipitated iron (if any) to bring into solution and was cooled to room temperature, the volume was made up to 20 mL. All analysis for arsenic was performed within one to two days of sample collection.

Preparation of sediment samples :

0.5 g of air dried sample was first moistened with water and then digested slowly with the addition of (1 : 3) perchloric acid : nitric acid mixture on a temperature controlled hot plate. After full evaporation of acid, the digested sample was leached with 25 ml water and 2 ml of hydrochloric acid and filtered through Whatman 40 filter paper, washed and the volume of the filtrate was made up to 50 ml. Sediment samples were analysed by conventional method.

Table 2. Arsenic concentration in sediments at different depths in borehole. (Estimated by silver diethy dithio carbamate method on 1987)

Bore hole depth (ft)	Nadia	Barasat	Mineral rich sample
	Concn. of As in (µg/g)	Concn. of As in (µg/g)	Concn. of As in (µg/g)
1-10 (clay)	4.8	B.D.L.	B.D.L.
10-20 (clay and sandclay)	6.4	B.D.L.	B.D.L.
20-30 (clay)	12.6	B.D.L.	B.D.L.
30-40 (clay)	B.D.L.	17.6	2.0
40-50 (clay)	B.D.L.	17.8	B.D.L.
50-60 (clay)	B.D.L.	B.D.L.	B.D.L.
60-70	B.D.L.	1.0	B.D.L.
70-80	B.D.L.	B.D.L.	B.D.L.
80-90	B.D.L.	B.D.L.	nd
90-100	B.D.L.	B.D.L.	nd
180-190 (sand and clay)	nd	3.1	nd
190-200 (clay)	nd	B D.L.	B.D.L.
200-210 (clay)	nd	B.D.L.	nd
210-220 (clay)	nd	0.2	nd
220-230 (clay)	nd	13.6	nd
230-240	nd	5.6	nd
240-250	nd	B.D.L.	nd
250-260	nd	B.D.L.	nd
260-270	nd	B.D.L.	nd
270-280	nd	B.D.L.	nd
280-290	nd	5.0	nd
290-300	nd	B.D.L.	nd

B.D.L. = Below Detection Limit, where detection limit is 0.2 µg/g.

nd = Not determined.

Prior to analysis (by FIAS-AAS) arsenic standards and digested samples (5 ml) were treated with 2 ml concentrated HCl and subsequently 5% (w/v) KI solution (2.5 ml) for complete reduction of all As⁵⁺ to As³⁺ and were kept at room temperature for 10 min and then introduced into sample tubing inlet and reduced to AsH₃ in reaction and goes through gas liquid separator to quartz cell by inert gas flow (50 mL/min) and analysis were performed.

Standard solutions of arsenic 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0 µg/L were used to obtain calibration curves. Samples were analysed and estimated from the instant calibration curve. Throughout this study, the sensitivity, practical quantitation limit and % standard deviations were determined and monitored.

Conclusion :

The detailed analytical technique described in this paper can be used as most modern method to determine total

arsenic content in the drinking water sample accurately below parts per billion levels (0.04 µg/L). Bar graph for detection of arsenic from random water sample analysis shows that irrespective of arsenic prone and non prone areas, arsenic concentrations are high in shallow level.

This sophisticated instrumental data also supports the earlier investigated (1987) bore hole sediment results analysed by Ag-diethyldithio carbamate method (sensitivity < .02 µg/ml or 0.2 µg/g in sediment). From the study we may infer that arsenic concentration is maximum in tubewell tapping shallow zone or well in shallow level. Arsenic concentration is more in clay layer than in sand layer. Generally base line concentration of arsenic in soils are in the order of 5-10 mg/kg and in agricultural belt it is enhanced more due to the use of fertilizer and arsenicals as insecticides, herbicides or pesticides. Though arsenical insecticides are now a days replaced mostly by other insecticides but the huge amount of phosphate

fertilizer must contain arsenic or arsenate, because both PO_4^{3-} and arsenate have very similar chemical nature. So arsenical pesticide-residue, fertilizer used and high iron content aggravate the situation. On the other hand, freshly prepared Fe_2O_3 and clay layer absorbed and retained arsenic and the tube wells spread the arsenic around it (rapidly through the strainer) and help *desorptions* so the picture may be clear why the tube well waters are mostly contaminated and why the arsenic contamination is widely spread in agricultural lands and villages. The *anthropogenic* sources should seriously be studied and of course with a method which can accurately detect the element in far below its permissible range.

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